

ESD protection design in a-IGZO TFT technologies

M. Scholz, S. Steudel, K. Myny, S. Chen, R. Boschke *, G. Hellings, D. Linten

imec, Kapeldreef 75, 3000 Leuven, Belgium

*also at KU Leuven, ESAT, Leuven

tel.: +3216288950, e-mail: mirko.scholz@imec.be

Abstract – Thin Film Transistor (TFT) with amorphous Indium-Gallium-Zinc-Oxide (a-IGZO) as channel material are characterized with TLP and HBM testing. The low mobility of the a-IGZO channel results in an ESD robustness of only 0.3 mA/um. This makes ESD protection design in a TFT technology a challenging task.

I. Introduction

Thin film transistor (TFT) are widely used for displays and X-ray imager. They are used as active matrix TFT backplanes and in circuits like gate driver integrated in panel (GIP). Recently, flexible AMOLED displays appeared [1]. In analog design flexible RF tags for near-field communication (NFC) are realized [2]. TFT are also integrated in the CMOS backend of line to enable interfaces between the low-voltage core circuit and I/O operating at higher voltages [3]. Because of the various applications ESD characterization of TFT devices got a lot of attention in the recent years [4-7]. Usually only the ESD robustness of TFT is reported. No further attention was given to ESD protection design. This work analyzes the ESD performance of the given TFT technology and applies the results to ESD protection design.

TFT have been made with poly crystalline or amorphous silicon or organic materials as channel material. Today, amorphous Indium-Gallium-Zinc-Oxide (a-IGZO) is the most common channel material. This is because of its significant improved mobility over materials like amorphous silicon.

In this work we introduce first the technology and devices under test (DUT). ESD testing with both TLP and HBM is carried out under different bias conditions and device configurations. The obtained results are benchmarked against the literature. Finally, the results are combined in a design case where a design window is defined for the ESD protection in an a-IGZO technology.

II. Technology and DUT

The devices in this work are manufactured in a self-aligned TFT architecture on a glass substrate with a flexible polyimide layer to enable flexible displays or circuits [2]. A barrier layer separates this substrate from the a-IGZO layer (Figure 1). The gate stack is formed by 100 nm SiO_2 on top of the a-IGZO layer. Molybdenum is used as gate metal. Source and drain areas are contacted with a Titanium-Aluminum metal stack. The a-IGZO layer is N-doped with hydrogen in the source and drain areas to improve the contact resistance. Finally, silicon-nitride is used as passivation. The obtained TFT are unipolar n-type transistors with a channel mobility of $10 \text{ cm}^2/\text{Vs}$. The typical operating voltage range is 5 to 10 V.

Figure 1: TFT device cross-section with device terminals; D: drain, G: gate and S: source.

III. ESD characterization

The devices are stressed in two ways: with and without gate bias and in the so called diode mode where the gate is shorted to the drain. TLP stress of different duration and HBM stress are applied to assess the robustness and device behavior during ESD stress.

TLP stress with gate bias

Devices with a gate length of 5 μm are used for the experiments with floating gate. During TLP stress from drain to source, no channel conduction occurs. Only a very low drain to source leakage current is measured. At a drain-source voltage of 120 V the devices break down and go into failure. This breakdown voltage is similar for different device width (Figure 2).

Figure 2: TLP breakdown voltages for drain to source stress with floating gate. Gate length: 5 μm .

The gate oxide (GOX) breakdown voltage is typically the upper limit of an ESD protection design window. In this technology the GOX withstands a DC electrical field of 7 MV/cm [1]. Figure 3 summarizes the GOX breakdown voltages during 100 ns TLP stress for 15 μm wide TFT devices depending on the gate length. A GOX breakdown voltage of 90 V is obtained for a gate length of 1 μm . For a gate length of 2 and 5 μm the breakdown voltage increases to 120 V.

Figure 3: TLP breakdown voltages for gate to source stress with floating drain, device width: 15 μm .

Figure 4a shows the device response during TLP stress with different DC bias voltages at the gate. The drain current during TLP stress increases with increasing gate voltage. At a gate voltage of 10 V a maximum failure current I_{T2} of 3.7 mA obtained. These results are related to the low channel mobility. It results in a high channel resistance and a very low I_{T2} . The I-V curves show a slight drop of current around 20 V. It should be noted that the leakage does not change. Thus the current drop in the I-V curve is not considered as failure. Additional analysis is ongoing to explain this effect in detail. This analysis could not be finished before the final deadline of this work.

In Figure 4b the gate length is varied to study the impact on the channel conduction. The current is normalized to the device width to include more gate length variations in this comparison. For a fixed gate voltage a shorter gate length leads to an increased channel conductance and thus failure level.

Figure 4: 100 ns TLP stress with applied gate bias: a) Variation of gate voltage for a constant gate length of 2 μm ; b) Variation of the gate length for a constant gate voltage of 10 V; device width: 250 μm .

100 ns TLP stress in diode mode

Previous work [6, 7] demonstrates that the best ESD performance w.r.t. to failure current and on-resistance is obtained if TFT are stressed in diode mode. In this mode the gate is shorted to the drain. During ESD stress the gate is biased with drain-source voltages which operate the devices with maximum channel conductance. To determine the failure level the leakage at a drain-source DC voltage of -5 V is monitored before and after each stress. Since the TFT in this work are n-type transistors they are fully turned off at this voltage. Figure 5a shows the TLP I-V curves and Figure 5b the leakage evolution for three device variations stressed in diode mode. Two observations are made. The I_{T2} reaches only 80 mA for a 250 μm wide device. Very large R_{ON} from 500 Ω to several k Ω are measured.

Figure 5: 100 ns TLP testing in diode mode: a) TLP I-V curves and b) leakage evolution; gate length: 2 μm .

In Figure 6 the intrinsic failure current and R_{ON} are plotted for different device widths. The TFT show a good width scaling even for very wide devices. The intrinsic failure current is around 0.3 mA/ μm . This is only one third of the typical intrinsic failure current of 1 mA/ μm in MOS channels.

Figure 6: Intrinsic failure current and R_{ON} of TFT with different width stressed in diode mode; gate length: 2 μm .

Figure 7 compares the failure current normalized on the $width \times gate \ length$ area with data from literature for TFT with different channel materials. The obtained robustness in this work is two times higher than the best device found in literature. This can be attributed to the self-aligned TFT architecture and higher mobility channel material used to manufacture the devices in this study. The other devices were made with an etch stop layer (ESL) or back channel etch (BCE) and different channel materials.

Figure 7: Comparison of the failure current normalized on $width \times gate \ length$ area during 100 ns TLP stress for different channel materials and TFT type found in literature.

Long duration TLP stress

Self-heating and heat management are often a challenge in TFT technologies since the substrate which is made of glass and plastic foil allows hardly any heat dissipation. Long duration TLP stress is used to investigate if the TFT devices show significant self-heating. Increasing the pulse width allows the amplification of possible self-heating.

Figure 8a shows the failure current I_{T2} depending on the stress duration for three devices with different width. With increasing pulse width the failure current

decreases. Figure 8b shows the extracted on-resistance of the same devices. For all four devices the on-resistance increases with increasing pulse width. Each on-resistance value is extracted from a TLP I-V curve which is plotted with an averaging window from 70 to 90 % of the pulse width. Thus the observed increase of the on-resistance during longer stressed is caused by the self-heating of the device. Overall the observed self-heating is much smaller compared to e.g. Silicon-On-Insulator (SOI) technologies known for the strong self-heating during ESD stress.

Figure 8: Long duration TLP stress on TFT with different width: a) TLP failure currents and b) on-resistance of TFT stressed in diode mode depending on the pulse width; gate length: 2 μm

HBM testing

Figure 9a summarizes the HBM failure level captured in diode mode on wafer-level for three device variations. Similar to the TLP characterization low failure level during HBM stress are obtained. A 250 μm wide device passes only 200 V HBM. This failure level is only a little higher than the 100 V HBM in the current *S20.20* specification [10]. Advanced ESD control measures are required when

packaging and handling these devices. Figure 9b shows a micrograph of a 100 μm wide device after HBM failure. A thermally induced damage in the a-IGZO layer can be seen. The failure signature is symmetrical which proves a uniform current flow in the multi-finger device during ESD stress.

Figure 9: HBM testing of TFT devices in diode mode: a) HBM failure level for three device widths and b) micrograph of a 100 μm wide TFT device after failure; gate length: 2 μm.

HBM testing is a product qualification test. Thus TLP data used during protection design needs to be verified with HBM testing. It has been shown that when testing high impedance devices HBM-TLP miscorrelation can occur [8]. Figure 10a analyzes the correlation between HBM and TLP stress. There is a good correlation between HBM and TLP testing. Similar HBM peak current at failure and TLP I_{T2} are obtained. In Figure 10b the voltage and current waveform during a HBM stress of 200 V are plotted. No voltage or current overshoot occur. Figure 10c overlays a HBM I-V curve [9] and with a 100 ns TLP I-V curve from the same device. In a HBM I-V curve the voltage and current are plotted for each point in time. During the first 80 ns of the HBM pulse, between a current of 60 and 80 mA, the HBM I-V curve deviates from the TLP I-V curve. This is caused by the device self-heating which leads to an increased resistance during TLP stress.

Figure 10: TLP - HBM correlation: a) HBM peak current during failure and TLP failure current for three device widths, b) voltage and current waveform during 200 V HBM stress, c) overlay of HBM and TLP I-V curve for a 250 μm wide device; gate length: 2 μm.

The TLP I-V curve is plotted from data which is averaged from 70 and 90 ns. At this moment the TFT conducts for a longer period of time. The HBM I-V curve includes also transient information which makes the change of resistance due to the device self-heating visible. A similar resistance in TLP and HBM can only be seen in the HBM I-V curve below a current

level of 60 mA. This current corresponds to a time after 80 ns during HBM stress.

IV. ESD protection design

The previous sections analyzed the behavior of the TFT under ESD stress. In this section we will apply the obtained results in an ESD protection design case of an 12 bit NFC transponder [2] manufactured in the same TFT technology with a-IGZO as channel material. Although the typical operating voltage of the technology is around 5 V already lower voltages are sufficient to enable a stable operation of the NFC circuit. Table 1 summarizes typical operation conditions of the circuit at low voltages. The design case is applied to the operating range of 1 V. This corresponds to V_{BIAS} of 2 V. At this voltage the circuit achieves a data rate complying with the ISO 15693 RFID/NFC standard.

Table 1: Data rate of NFC transponder circuit depending on the operation condition, data taken from [2].

	Minimum	Typical	Maximum
V_{BIAS} [V]	1	2	20
V_{DD} [V]	0.5	1	10
Data rate [kb/s]	14.3	26.48	396.5

An *unprotected* NFC transponder circuit (Figure 11a) is stressed with HBM testing to access its intrinsic ESD robustness. For two pin combinations, V_{BIAS} to V_{DD} and V_{DD} to GND , the circuit passes a HBM stress of only 80 V. This is below the recommended minimum protection level of 100 V HBM in the *S20.20* specification of the ESDA.

TFT in diode configuration are used to protect the V_{BIAS} input (Figure 11b). Since the V_{DD} is only 1 V and the V_{TI} is around 6 V also the supply pins can be protected with a TFT in diode configuration without interfering with the normal circuit operation. Figure 11c shows the TLP I-V curves for two pin combinations, V_{BIAS} to V_{DD} and V_{DD} to GND . The TFT are designed in diode configuration with a gate length of 2 μm and a width of 250 μm. The design window is defined by a V_{BIAS} of 2 V as a lower limit and the GOX breakdown of 120 V as an upper limit. The protection design passes 200 V HBM which is sufficient for packaging and handling the circuit in an ESD controlled environment.

Figure 11: ESD protection design of a TFT based NFC transistor: a) micrograph of unprotected circuit; b) schematic of the full protection design for $V_{BIAS} = 2$ V; c) definition of design window for the ESD protection design, lower limit: bias voltage V_{BIAS} , upper limit: GOX breakdown voltage $V_{BD, GOX}$ during 100 ns TLP stress; TFT devices: width of 250 μm and gate length of 2 μm .

One could argue that a protection level of 200 V HBM is not sufficient from a product point of view. Currently the industry wide HBM protection level is 1 kV. This results in a clamp width of at least 1 mm

for both the bias input and the power clamp. Even if the clamp is placed in a multi-finger layout the protection design would result in very a large area penalty. A possible alternative for such protection level can be the use of discrete components like Transient-Voltage Suppressors (TVS). In a co-packaging approach the TVS are added to the NFC circuit using flex bonds with an anisotropic conductive adhesive. A similar packaging approach is used for the manufacturing of flexible AMOLED displays where CMOS driver ICs are connected to the display [1].

The co-design approach known from system-level ESD protection design [11, 12] is applied to match the device response of a TVS device to the on-chip protection of the TFT circuit. Figure 12 shows the TLP I-V curves of a TVS diode with a turn-on voltage of 7.5 V and the V_{bias} to GND protection path of the design case (Figure 12). The large on-resistance and high GOX breakdown voltage of the TFT devices allow to use these TVS based ESD protection on both component and system level. In the proposed design the TVS diode protects only the V_{BIAS} input. The supply pins of the circuit are protected with the supply decoupling network which is usually present on the board.

Figure 12: TLP I-V of a TVS and the V_{BIAS} to GND protection path.

V. Conclusions

TFT with a-IGZO as channel material are characterized with TLP and HBM testing. The low mobility of the a-IGZO channel results in a large R_{ON} and a low ESD robustness. During TLP stress an ESD robustness of 0.3 mA/ μm is obtained when stressed in diode mode. The analysis of the thermal behavior with long duration TLP stress shows only little self-heating in these devices during ESD stress. TLP and HBM testing results are combined in a design case. The proposed on-chip protection for the input pin and the

supply pins passes 200 V HBM if 250 μm wide TFTs are used in diode configuration for the input protection and as power clamp. Significant higher ESD robustness level are achievable with discrete TVS devices which are added to the TFT circuit through gluing or bonding. The large on-resistance and the high gate oxide breakdown voltages of the TFT enable a robust ESD protection for both component- and system-level requirements with TVS devices.

Acknowledgment

This work has been supported by the Flemish IWT project ORCA. It has also received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 644331 (PING project).

The authors would like to thank the mentor, Dr. Zhong Chen, for the detailed review and his suggestions for the improvement of the manuscript.

References

- [1] S. Steudel, et al, "Flexible AMOLED Display with Integrated Gate Driver Operating at Operation Speed Compatible with 4k2k," SID Symposium Dig. Tech. Pap., 2015.
- [2] K. Myny and S. Steudel, "Flexible Thin-Film NFC Transponder Chip Exhibiting Data Rates Compatible to ISO NFC Standards Using Self-Aligned Metal-Oxide TFTs", ISSCC, 2016.
- [3] K. Kaneko, et al, "A novel BEOL transistor (BETr) with InGaZnO embedded in Cu-interconnects for on-chip high voltage I/Os in standard CMOS LSIs," VLSI Symposium, 2011.
- [4] M. Ker, et al, "Correlation between transmission-line-pulsing I-V curve and human-body-model ESD level on low temperature poly-Si TFT devices," IPFA, 2004.
- [5] M. Ker, et al, "Investigation on ESD Robustness of P-type TFTs under Different Layout Structures in L TPS Process for On-Panel ESD Protection Design", International ESD Workshop, 2007.
- [6] W. Liu, et al, "Study of organic thin-film transistors under electrostatic discharge stresses," IEEE Electron Device Letters, 2011.
- [7] Y. H. Tai, et al, "Test and analysis of the ESD robustness for the diode-connected a-IGZO thin film transistors," IEEE/OSA Journal of Display Technology, 2013.
- [8] M. Scholz, et al, "ESD on-wafer characterization: Is TLP still the right measurement tool?," IEEE Transaction of Instrumentation and Measurements, 2009.
- [9] M. Scholz, et al, "Faster ESD device characterization with wafer-level HBM," IEEE ICMTS, 2007.
- [10] "ANSI/ESD S20.20-2014", ESD Association, 2014.
- [11] V. Vashchenko, M. Scholz, "System-level ESD protection", Springer Scientific, 2014.
- [12] "White Paper 3: System Level ESD Part I: Common Misconceptions and Recommended Basic Approaches", Industry Council on ESD Target Levels, 2010.